

Inter-District Variation and Economic Differentials in Fertility in India: Evidence from Population-based Survey Data

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Most studies on the variation of fertility analysis in India were restricted to the national and state levels and based on census data. Using the data from District Level Household Survey-3 (DLHS-3), 2007-08 and the 61st round of National Sample Survey (NSS), 2004-05 this paper examined the inter-district variation and economic differentials in total fertility rate (TFR) in India. The TFR for each district of India was estimated based on birth order statistics through regression method. Economic differentials in fertility were examined with respect to monthly per capita consumption expenditure (MPCE) class at the district level. Results indicate that there was a wide variation in TFR among the districts of India. The estimated TFR was found to be highest (6.1) in the district of Shahjahanpur of Uttar Pradesh and lowest (1.3) in the district of Mahe of Pondicherry. While the majority of the districts of the three southern states (Andhra Pradesh, Kerala, & Tamil Nadu) had TFR of replacement level or below replacement level (TFR of less than or equal to 2.1), the majority of the districts in northern states (mainly in Bihar & Uttar Pradesh) had TFR of more than 4. The level of fertility was found to vary across the districts with the level of MPCE. The districts with low levels of MPCE had higher fertility compared to the districts with high levels of MPCE. This clearly indicates that economically backward districts tend to have higher fertility compared to economically well-off districts in India.

Keywords: Total fertility rate, levels of total fertility, district-level variation in fertility, MPCE class

In 1952, India was the first country to launch the family welfare programme to control birth rates and thereby stabilize the population (MOHFW, 2000). During the last five decades of the twentieth century (1952-1994/1950s-1990s), the family welfare programme of India underwent several changes along with changes in targets, family planning methods and implementation strategies (Srinivasan, 1998). Additionally, the National Population Policy 2000 was introduced by the Government with its medium-term objective of achieving replacement level fertility by 2010 and long term objective to achieve population stabilization by 2045 (MOHFW, 2000). However, despite several efforts and a reduction in the growth rate of the population, the actual population size of India is increasing rapidly. According to the 2011 census of India, during the last six decades (1951-2011) India's population has increased by more than threefold; from 361 million in 1951 to 1210 million in 2011 (Das & Mohanty, 2012). Though the level of fertility is declining rapidly in India, there is considerable variation in fertility levels among the states of India (Guilmoto & Irudaya Rajan, 2013). Some states such as Bihar, Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh and Assam continue to have high fertility. More than half of the states of India have fertility above the replacement level (TFR of 2.1). Moreover, there is considerable variation in fertility levels even

among all districts of India and among the districts within different states of India (Mohanty et al., 2012). The districts of two larger states of India, namely Uttar Pradesh and Bihar continue to have relatively higher fertility (Das & Mohanty, 2012). The high fertility may not only affect the average progress at the household and individual level but also affect the average progress at the macro level (Das & Mohanty, 2012). Without the faster decline in fertility across the districts of India, the population stabilization in India can never be achieved.

In India, the districts are considered to be the basis of planning and programme implementation. The estimates of fertility are often required for implementing national and state planning and policies. It should be noted that, available studies on fertility analysis in India were confined to the national and state-level analyses. Though, in the recent past, some studies were carried out to provide the estimates of fertility for districts of India, most of them were based on census data only (Registrar General of India, 1989; 1997; Bhat, 1996; Prakasam et al., 2000; Guilmoto & Irudaya Rajan, 2002; Ram et al., 2005; Das & Mohanty, 2012; Mohanty et al., 2012). Even, there were not many studies focusing on the district-level differentials in fertility with respect to any economic indicator. In this context, in this paper, an attempt has been made to examine the inter-district variation and economic differentials in total fertility in India using population-based survey data, considering the districts as the units of analysis.

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Method

Participants

The purpose of this paper was to assess the extent of variations and economic differentials in fertility at the district level in India, for which the district-level estimates of total fertility rate (TFR) for the period 2007-2008 were considered. District Level Household Survey data of 2007-08 (DLHS-3) have been used to estimate the TFR. The estimates of TFR were derived for 587 districts of the 33

states of India (except for the districts of Jammu & Kashmir & Nagaland). The TFR for each district was estimated using birth order statistics. The DLHS under the Reproductive and Child Health (RCH) project has been designed by the Government of India to provide data on key RCH indicators at the district level. Additionally, the DLHS also intended to provide the information on facilities available in government health institutions and information on household assets and amenities. In DLHS-3, the data were collected from 7, 20,320 households covering 601 districts from 34 states (except Nagaland) of India. In DLHS-3, the individual level information was collected from ever-married women aged 15-49 years (N=6, 43,944) and unmarried women aged 15-24 years (N=1, 66,260). The individual level information for ever married women in DLHS-3 was collected on women's characteristics, maternal care including antenatal and postnatal care, child health care including immunization of children, use of contraception including knowledge about available contraceptive methods, children ever born and children surviving, fertility preference, reproductive health including awareness of RST/STI and HIV/AIDS, etc. Besides these, the DLHS-3 collected the detailed information on live births such as birth order, date of birth, surviving status and age at death of live-born children, etc. under all pregnancies that occurred to all ever-married women aged 15-49 years (excluding women whose gauna was not performed) since January 1, 2004. However, the estimates of TFR were confined to the live births taking place in the three years preceding the date of the survey. Besides the DLHS data, the household consumption expenditure data from the 61st round of National Sample Survey (NSS), 2004-05 were used to examine the economic differentials in fertility at the district level. In many population research and demographic surveys, the consumption data is considered to be more reliable than income data. The National Sample Survey (NSS) collects data on important socio-economic aspects on a comprehensive basis for the whole country by using scientific sampling techniques. Specifically, the data of the NSS 61st round (2004-05) was designed to provide the estimates at the district level. The household consumption expenditure data on all food and non-food items collected from 30-day as well as 365-day recall periods (mixed recall period) are used to compute the MPCE at the district level. It may be mentioned that the estimates for the districts of Jammu and Kashmir were not reliable and, therefore, the state of Jammu and Kashmir was exempted from the analysis.

Measures

Estimation of TFR: In this paper, the TFR at the district level in India has been estimated through regression-based method. First, the regression coefficients have been obtained by regressing birth order with TFR for the states of India. Ram et al. (2005) had used regression methods (both linear & exponential) to estimate TFR for districts of India. They had used the combined-percentage of first and second order births as an independent variable and the TFR as a dependent variable from the census in order to determine the regression coefficients. The similar procedure has been followed here to estimate the TFR for all districts of India. However, in this paper, the percentage of birth order 3 and above (BOD3+) from DLHS-3 was used for estimating TFR through regression method. First, two regression analyses (linear & exponential) were carried out at the state level, the TFR and percentage of BOD3+ being the dependent and independent variables, respectively. This was done separately for the state-level data of 2007, 2008, and the combined rural and urban data of 2007 and 2008 available from the SRS

statistical reports 2007 and 2008 (Registrar General of India, 2008; 2009a). The regression equations used to compute the regression coefficients are as follows:

$$TFR = a + b * BOD3+ \text{-----} (1)$$

$$TFR = e^{(a + b * BOD3+)} \text{-----} (2)$$

Where, 'a' is the intercept, 'b' is the regression coefficient and BOD3+ is the percentage of birth order 3 and above.

These two regressions were run to identify the coefficient with a higher level of significance and minimum standard error and, consequently, to identify the regression equation suitable for estimating TFR for districts of India. It was found that the values of regression coefficient (b) appeared to be significant and positive for all regressions, indicating a positive relationship between the TFR and the percentage of BOD3+. However, the standard error for exponential regression for pooled data from 2007 and 2008 was found to be minimum (0.001). This implies that the association between the TFR and the percentage of BOD3+ was much stronger for exponential regression for pooled data from 2007 and 2008 than for all other cases. The scatter diagram (Figure1) also shows that the TFR was not linearly associated with percentage of BOD3+, but the relationship between these two was found to be curvilinear. Thus, the coefficient values derived from exponential regression for pooled data from 2007 and 2008 had been used for estimating district-level TFR. The exponential regression equation used to estimate the district-level TFR is as follows:

$$TFR = e^{(0.216 + 0.024 * BOD3+)} \text{-----} (3)$$

Bivariate Analysis

A bivariate analysis was carried out to examine the economic-differentials in fertility among the districts of India based on MPCE class (in ₹) and levels of TFR. For this purpose, the estimates of MPCE for districts of India were derived from the 61st round of NSS, 2004-05. The total monthly household consumption expenditure is divided by total household size to get the MPCE at the district level. Since the number of districts in DLHS varies with that of NSS, this particular analysis was restricted to 581 districts from 33 states (except the districts of Jammu & Kashmir & Nagaland) of India for simplicity of analysis, taking the availability of data for the districts available from both the data sources into consideration.

However, the economic differentials in fertility were examined with reference to MPCE class defined based on the district level MPCE, as of 2004-05. Four MPCE class categories were defined based on the mean value and standard deviation (considering standard deviation as an interval) in MPCE for 581 districts of India;

low (MPCE \leq ₹ 433), lower middle (MPCE of ₹ 434-681), higher middle (MPCE of ₹ 682-930) and high (MPCE \geq ₹ 931) categories. The levels of TFR were categorized into four different categories such as less than or equal to 2.1, 2.2-3.0, 3.1-4.0, and more than 4.0.

Results

Reliability of the District-level Estimates of TFR

In order to understand the reliability of the district-level estimates of TFR in India, the state-level estimates of TFR derived from DLHS-3 are compared with those of SRS 2006 (Registrar General of India, 2007) (Table 1). In addition, the correlation coefficient between the state-level estimates of TFR derived from DLHS-3 and the state-

level estimates of TFR from SRS 2006 is examined. The estimates of TFR derived from DLHS-3 can be referred to those of 2006. This is because the percentage of BOD3+ was computed from the births that took place in the 3 years preceding the date of the survey. Therefore, the estimates of TFR may be referred to that of 2006. It was observed that the estimated TFR for India derived from DLHS-3 was very close to that from SRS 2006. The TFR of India derived from DLHS-3 was 3.1 and that from SRS 2006 was 2.8. In addition, the actual differences between the state-level estimates of TFR derived from DLHS-3 and that of SRS 2006 were marginal. In other words, the state level estimates derived from DLHS-3 were close to that of SRS 2006.

Table 1

Comparison of Estimated TFR Derived from DLHS-3 with that of SRS 2006 in the States of India

States/Union territories	Total fertility rate		Actual Difference col.1-col.2	Percentage of birth order 3 & above (DLHS-3)
	DLHS-3	SRS 2006 (2)		
Andaman & Nicobar Islands	1.9	--	--	16.9
Andhra Pradesh	1.9	2.0	-0.1	18.1
Arunachal Pradesh	2.9	--	--	35.0
Assam	2.9	2.7	0.2	35.8
Bihar	4.5	4.2	0.3	54.0
Chandigarh	2.0	--	--	19.4
Chhattisgarh	3.4	3.3	0.1	41.6
Dadra & Nagar Haveli	3.3	--	--	40.4
Daman & Diu	2.5	--	--	29.9
Delhi	2.6	2.1	0.5	30.6
Goa	1.9	--	--	17.8
Gujarat	2.8	2.7	0.1	33.3
Haryana	2.8	2.7	0.1	34.0
Himachal Pradesh	2.1	2.0	0.1	22.1
Jammu & Kashmir@	--	--	--	--
Jharkhand	3.9	3.4	0.5	47.5
Karnataka	2.6	2.1	0.5	31.3
Kerala	1.8	1.7	0.1	15.7
Lakshadweep	3.2	--	--	39.0
Madhya Pradesh	2.7	3.5	-0.8	32.8
Maharashtra	2.4	2.1	0.3	26.8
Manipur	3.3	--	--	40.9
Meghalaya	3.7	--	--	45.0
Mizoram	2.7	--	--	32.1
Nagaland#	--	--	--	--
Odisha	2.7	2.5	0.2	32.2
Pondicherry	1.5	--	--	8.7
Punjab	2.2	2.1	0.1	24.6
Rajasthan	3.2	3.5	-0.3	39.4
Sikkim	2.6	--	--	31.1
Tamil Nadu	1.9	1.7	0.2	17.3
Tripura	2.5	--	--	28.5
Uttar Pradesh	4.6	4.2	0.4	54.8
Uttarakhand	2.9	--	--	35.1
West Bengal	2.4	2.0	0.4	27.8
All India*	3.1	2.8	0.3	37.9

Note. *Excluding Jammu & Kashmir and Nagaland. @Not considered in the analysis. #Not covered by DLHS-3. - -Not available

The correlation coefficient of state-level estimates of TFR derived from DLHS-3 and the state-level estimates of TFR from SRS 2006 was estimated to be 0.926. This suggests that the estimates derived from DLHS-3 can be satisfactory and acceptable.

Inter-district Differences in TFR

To understand the inter-district differences in the levels of TFR, the percent distribution of districts by levels of TFR for India and its states were examined. For this purpose, the districts had been classified into four categories: districts with TFR ≤ 2.1 , with TFR of 2.2-3.0, with TFR of 3.1-4.0, and with TFR > 4.0 . It was noticed that 37.8 percent districts (222) had TFR between 2.2-3.0, 20 percent districts (118) had TFR between 3.1-4.0 and 19.3 percent districts (113) had TFR above 4.0. However, only 22.8 percent of districts (134 out of 587) had replacement level or below replacement level fertility (TFR of ≤ 2.1). About 40 percent districts (231 out of 587) had TFR of more than 3.

The distribution pattern of the districts by TFR levels was not similar across the states (Table 2). For instance, in Andhra Pradesh, out of 23 districts, 21 had TFR of replacement level or below replacement level and the remaining 2 districts had TFR between 2.2-3.0. Similarly, in Tamil Nadu, out of 30 districts, 26 had TFR of replacement level or below replacement level and the remaining 4 districts had TFR between 2.2-3.0. On the other hand, most of the districts of Uttar Pradesh and Bihar (57 out of 70 districts of Uttar Pradesh & 33 out of 37 districts of Bihar) had TFR above 4 and no district of these states had reached replacement level of fertility.

Inter-District Variation in Fertility

Inter-district variation in fertility in India was examined in terms of estimated TFR of 2006 at the district level. The estimates of TFR, as of 2006, showed that the level of TFR largely varies across the Indian districts. The level of TFR, as of 2006, was found to be lowest in six districts of Jammu and Kashmir (such as Palwama, Anantanag,

Table 2

Distribution of Districts by Levels of Total Fertility Rate and States, India, 2006

States	Total Fertility Rate				Total number of districts
	≤ 2.1	2.2-3.0	3.1-4.0	> 4.0	
Andaman & Nicobar Islands	2				2
Andhra Pradesh	21	2			23
Arunachal Pradesh	2	8	6		16
Assam	3	16	7	1	27
Bihar			4	33	37
Chandigarh	1				1
Chhattisgarh		4	11	1	16
Dadra & Nagar Haveli			1		1
Daman & Diu	1	1			2
Delhi	2	7			9
Goa	1	1			2
Gujarat	3	16	5	1	25
Haryana	1	18		1	20
Himachal Pradesh	6	5	1		12
Jharkhand		2	11	9	22
Karnataka	9	11	7		27
Kerala	12	2			14
Lakshadweep			1		1
Madhya Pradesh	9	21	13	2	45
Maharashtra	13	21	1		35
Manipur		4	3	2	9
Meghalaya		1	4	2	7
Mizoram		6	2		8
Odisha	2	21	5	2	30
Pondicherry	4				4
Punjab	6	14			20
Rajasthan		11	19	2	32
Sikkim		4			4
Tamil Nadu	26	4			30
Tripura	2	2			4
Uttar Pradesh		1	12	57	70
Uttarakhand		10	3		13
West Bengal	8	9	2		19
All India*	134	222	118	113	587

Note. *Excluding Jammu and Kashmir and Nagaland

Srinagar, Barmula, Badgam), and one district of Pondicherry (namely Mahe) (1.3), followed by Guntur of Andhra Pradesh, Pathanamthitta, Idukki and Kollam of Kerala, and Erode, Kanniyakumari and Coimbatore of Tamil Nadu (1.4) and highest in Shahjahanpur of Uttar Pradesh (6.1), followed by Mewat of Haryana (5.9). It was also observed that the majority of the districts from four southern states of India (such as Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala and Tamil Nadu, and one western state, namely, Maharashtra) had reached below replacement level fertility. The inter-district variation in fertility is also evident from the mapping of districts developed based on estimated TFR (see Figure 2). From Figure 2, it is evident that the districts of northern and north-eastern states of India tend to have high fertility (TFR of more than 3) in contrary to the districts of other parts of India.

Figure 2: Mapping of districts based on total fertility rate, India, 2007-08.

Economic Differentials in Fertility

Table 3 presents the distribution of districts by MPCE class and levels of TFR in India. It was observed that the level of TFR largely varies among the districts of different MPCE class categories. Among the districts in low MPCE class, about 45% districts had a TFR of above 4 and only 3% districts had TFR of less than or equal to 2.1. On the contrary, only 8% districts in higher middle and 3% districts in high MPCE class categories had TFR of above 4, while 28% districts in higher middle and 47% districts in high MPCE class categories had TFR of less than or equal to 2.1. In general, it is observed that, the level of fertility varies across the districts with reference to the levels of MPCE. The districts with low levels of MPCE had higher fertility compared to the districts with high levels of MPCE. This clearly indicates that economically backward districts tend to have higher fertility compared to economically well-off districts. The list of districts identified with low levels of MPCE and high levels of TFR may be useful for effective programme intervention with regard to the reduction of fertility in the economically backward districts in India. The list of districts with low levels of MPCE and high levels of TFR by states of India is given in the Appendix.

Table 3

Percent Distribution of Districts by MPCE Class and Levels of TFR, India

MPCE Class (in ₹)	Levels of TFR				Total
	<=2.1	2.2-3.0	3.1-4.0	>4.0	
Low (<= 433)	3.0 (2)	26.9 (18)	25.4 (17)	44.8 (30)	100.0 (67)
Lower middle (434-681)	17.7 (48)	30.9 (84)	26.5 (72)	25.0 (68)	100.0 (272)
Higher middle (682-930)	27.9 (46)	50.3 (83)	13.9 (23)	7.9 (13)	100.0 (165)
High (>= 931)	46.8 (36)	42.9(33)	7.8 (6)	2.6 (2)	100.0 (77)
All India*	22.7 (132)	37.5 (218)	20.3 (118)	19.5 (113)	100.0 (581)

Note. *Excluding the districts of Jammu and Kashmir, Nagaland, and four districts of Delhi (North, East, New Delhi and Central), one district of Maharashtra (Mumbai) and one district of Andaman and Nicobar Islands (Nicobar). Note: Figures in the parentheses represents the number of districts.

Summary and Conclusion

The purpose of this paper was to examine the inter-district variation and economic differentials in fertility among the district of India. The TFR, a vital indicator of fertility, was considered for the purpose of this paper. The analysis clearly showed that wide variations in TFR among the districts of India continued to exist. Among the districts under consideration, about 40% districts (231 out of 587) had TFR of above 3. Surprisingly, among the districts having TFR≥3, about 75% districts (174 out of 231) are mainly from six of the eight Empowered Action Group states of India, namely, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Jharkhand, Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan and Uttar Pradesh. On the other hand, only 23% districts (134 out of 587) had achieved replacement level or below replacement level of fertility. Among these districts, more than 50% districts (72 out of 134) are mainly from three southern states (Andhra Pradesh, Kerala, & Tamil Nadu) and one western state (Maharashtra) of India. In overall, it was found that the districts of northern states such as Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Jharkhand, Madhya Pradesh, Odisha, Rajasthan and Uttar Pradesh tend to have higher levels of fertility. This indicates the fact that the districts of these states were lagging behind in demographic advancement. These findings were also similar to that of some other studies (Guilmoto & Irudaya Rajan, 2002; Mohanty et al., 2012; Registrar General of India, 2009b; Das, 2022). Even, the districts of those states were also economically lagging behind. The incidence of being higher levels of fertility in the districts of northern states of India might be due to the fact that these districts were socio-economically backward (Das, 2013). Not only that, the incidence of higher infant mortality (Das, 2017) and lower utilization of reproductive and child health care services (Das, 2015) might be responsible for higher fertility in the districts of northern states of India. The bivariate analysis of MPCE class and levels of TFR showed that among the districts falling under low MPCE class, about 45% districts had TFR of more than 4 and only 3% districts had TFR of less than or equal to 2.1. On the other hand, among the districts of high MPCE class category, only 3% districts had TFR of more than 4 while 47% districts had TFR of less than or equal to 2.1. This indicates the fact that the districts with lower levels of MPCE had higher fertility compared to the districts with higher levels of MPCE. This further implies that the economically backward districts tend to have higher levels of fertility compared to economically well-off

districts in India. However, there is scope for researchers to go for similar kind of analysis based on other or current population-based

survey data and, accordingly, compare the results with this paper as well as to look into the trends of fertility at the district level in India.

Appendix

List of Districts with a High Level of TFR and a Low Level of MPCE and a High Level of TFR by States, India

States	Districts with a high level of TFR (TFR > 3)	Districts with low level of MPCE (MPCE < ₹433) and high level of TFR (TFR > 3)
Andhra Pradesh	NA	NA
Arunachal Pradesh	East Kameng, Lohit, Lower Dibang Valley, Papum Pare, Upper Siang, Upper Subansiri	NA
Assam	Cachar, Chirang, Hailakandi, Karimganj, Nagaon, Sonitpur, Tinsukia, Udalguri	NA
Bihar	Araria, Aurangabad, Banka, Begusarai, Bhagalpur, Bhojpur, Buxar, Darbhanga, Gaya, Gopalganj, Jamui, Jehanabad, Kaimur Bhabua, Katihar, Khagaria, Kishanganj, Lakhisarai, Madhepura, Madhubani, Munger, Muzaffarpur, Nalanda, Nawada, Pashchim Champaran, Patna, Purba Champaran, Purnia, Rohtas, Saharsa, Samastipur, Saran, Sheikhpura, Sheohar, Sitamarhi, Siwan, Supaul, Vaishali	Araria, Aurangabad, Banka, Begusarai, Buxar, Jamui, Jehanabad, Kaimur Bhabua, Madhubani, Muzaffarpur, Pashchim Champaran, Samastipur, Saran
Chhattisgarh	Bastar, Bilaspur, Dantewada, Janjgir-Champa, Jashpur, Kanker, Kawardha, Korba, Koriya, Raigarh, Rajnandgaon, Surguja	Bastar, Dantewada, Kanker, Kawardha, Surguja
Dadra & Nagar Haveli	Dadra & Nagar Haveli	NA
Delhi	NA	NA
Gujarat	Dohad, Kachchh, Narmada, Patan, Sabar Kantha, The Dangs	The Dangs
Haryana	Mewat	NA
Himachal Pradesh	Lahul & Spiti	NA
Jharkhand	Bokaro, Chatra, Deoghar, Dhanbad, Garhwa, Giridih, Godda, Gumla, Hazaribagh, Jamtara, Kodarma, Latehar, Lohardaga, Pakaur, Palamu, Pashchimi Singhbhum, Ranchi, Sahibganj, Saraikela Khaseswan, Simdega	Chatra, Gumla, Jamtara, Latehar, Lohardaga, Pakaur, Palamu, Sahibganj, Simdega
Karnataka	Bagalkot, Bidar, Bijapur, Gadag, Gulbarga, Haveri, Koppal	NA
Lakshadweep	Lakshadweep	NA
Madhya Pradesh	Barwani, Betul, Bhopal, Chhatarpur, Dhar, Harda, Hoshangabad, Jhabua, Raisen, Satna, Sehore, Sheopur, Sidhi, Umaria, West Nimar	Betul, Chhatarpur, Jhabua, Raisen, Umaria
Maharashtra	Nandurbar	NA
Manipur	Chandel, Churachandpur, Senapati, Tamenglong, Ukhrul	NA
Mizoram	Lawngtlai, Lunglei	NA
Meghalaya	East Garo Hills, Jaintia Hills, Ri Bhoi, South Garo Hills, West Garo Hills, West Khasi Hills	NA
Orissa	Balangir, Gajapati, Kalahandi, Kandhamal, Malkangiri, Nabarangapur, Rayagada	Balangir, Gajapati, Kalahandi, Kandhamal, Malkangiri, Nabarangapur, Rayagada
Punjab	NA	NA
Rajasthan	Ajmer, Banswara, Baran, Barmer, Bharatpur, Bhilwara, Bikaner, Churu, Dausa, Dhaulpur, Dungarpur, Jaisalmer, Jalore, Jodhpur, Karauli, Nagaur, Pali, Rajsamand, Sirohi, Tonk, Udaipur	NA
Tamil Nadu	NA	NA
Uttar Pradesh	Agra, Aligarh, Allahabad, Ambedaker Nagar, Auraiya, Azamgarh, Baghpat, Bahraich, Ballia, Balrampur, Banda, Barabanki, Bareilly, Basti, Bijnor, Budaun, Bulandshahar, Chandauli, Chitrakoot, Deoria, Etah, Etawah, Faizabad, Farrukhabad, Fatehpur, Firozabad, Gautam Buddha Nagar, Ghaziabad, Ghazipur, Gonda, Gorakhpur, Hamirpur, Hardoi, Hathras, Jalaun, Jaunpur, Jyotiba Phule Nagar, Kannauj, Kanpur Dehat, Kanpur Nagar, Kaushambi, Kheri, Kushinagar, Lalitpur, Lucknow, Maharajganj, Mahoba, Mainpuri, Mathura, Mau, Meerut, Mirzapur, Moradabad, Muzaffarnagar, Pilibhit, Pratapgarh, Rae Bareilly, Rampur, Saharanpur, Sant Kabir Nagar, Sant Ravidas Nagar, Shahjahanpur, Shrawasti, Siddharthnagar, Sitapur, Sonbhadra, Sultanpur, Unnao, Varanasi	Agra, Aligarh, Allahabad, Ambedaker Nagar, Auraiya, Azamgarh, Baghpat, Bahraich, Ballia, Balrampur, Banda, Barabanki, Bareilly, Basti, Bijnor, Budaun, Bulandshahar, Chandauli, Nagar, Ghaziabad, Ghazipur, Gonda, Gorakhpur, Farrukhabad, Fatehpur, Firozabad, Gautam Buddha, Hamirpur, Hardoi, Hathras, Jalaun, Jaunpur, Jyotiba Phule Nagar, Kannauj, Kanpur Dehat, Kanpur Nagar, Kaushambi, Kheri, Kushinagar, Lalitpur, Lucknow,
Uttaranchal /Uttarakhand	Champawat, Dehradun, Hardwar	NA
West Bengal	Maldah, Uttar Dinajpur	NA

Note. NA: Not available (no district found in the low MPCE category with high fertility)

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